

THE POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE E-GOVERNMENT PROJECT

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Abstract. *The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the public administration system opens up new opportunities for the provision of public services, data management and citizen engagement. By automating processes, improving data analysis, and increasing the accuracy of decision-making, AI can optimize operations, reduce costs, and increase transparency. The article discusses the main features that AI offers as part of the implementation of the e-government concept, including advanced personalization of services, predictive analytics and national security. In addition, the article examines the problems associated with the implementation of AI, such as ethical aspects, the need for complex infrastructure and data privacy issues, and suggests strategies to maximize the potential of AI in public administration.*

Keywords: *automation, artificial intelligence, public administration; information and communication technologies; public services; open government; digitalization.*

Аннотация. *Сунъий интеллектнинг (АИ) давлат бошқаруви тизимида қўшилиши давлат хизматларини кўрсатиши, маълумотларни бошқариши ва фуқароларни эжалб қилиши учун янги имкониятлар очади. Жараёнларни автоматлаштириши, маълумотларни таҳлил қилишни такомиллаштириши ва қарор қабул қилишининг аниқлигини ошириши орқали АИ операцияларни оптималлаштириши, харажатларни камайтириши ва шаффофликни ошириши мумкин. Мақолада АИ электрон ҳукумат концепциясини амалга оширишининг бир қисми сифатида тақдим этилган асосий хусусиятлар, шу жумладан хизматларни илгор шахсийлаштириши, башоратли таҳлил ва миллий хавфсизлик муҳокама қилинади. Бундан ташқари, мақолада АИни амалга ошириши билан боғлиқ муаммолар, масалан, ахлоқий жиҳатлар, мураккаб инфратузилма ва маълумотлар махфийлиги масалалари кўриб чиқилади ва давлат бошқарувида АИ салоҳиятини максимал даражада ошириши стратегиялари таклиф этилади.*

Калит сўзлар: *автоматлаштириши, сунъий интеллект, давлат бошқаруви; ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари; давлат хизматлари; очиқ ҳукумат; рақамлаштириши.*

Аннотация. *Интеграция искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в систему государственного управления открывает новые возможности для предоставления государственных услуг, управления данными и вовлечения граждан. Автоматизируя процессы, улучшая анализ данных и повышая точность принятия решений, ИИ может оптимизировать операции, снизить затраты и повысить прозрачность системы государственного управления. В статье рассматриваются основные возможности, которые ИИ предлагает в рамках реализации концепции электронного правительства, включая расширенную персонализацию услуг, прогнозную аналитику и национальную безопасность. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются проблемы, связанные с внедрением ИИ, такие как этические аспекты, потребности в сложной инфраструктуре и вопросы конфиденциальности данных, а также предлагаются стратегии, позволяющие максимально использовать потенциал ИИ в государственном управлении.*

***Ключевые слова:** автоматизация, искусственный интеллект, государственное управление; информационно-коммуникационные технологии; государственные услуги; открытое правительство; цифровизация.*

The polystructural transformations observed in the social space since the end of the twentieth century are largely determined by the rapid development of digital technologies. The latter, of course, are primarily a technological phenomenon, but due to their role as determinants of social change, their significance goes far beyond the purely technical plane. Digital technologies are developing rapidly, moving from local spaces to global ones, so it can be argued that the digitalization of social space, coupled with the rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) technology, marks the formation of a new paradigm of social development.

Undoubtedly, artificial intelligence is one of the key technologies of our time. According to UN experts, the pursuit of dominance in artificial intelligence is the "space race" of our time [1]. Countries from all over the world are investing significant resources to create and improve their AI capabilities. More than 50 developed countries of the world have already created and approved national strategies for the development of artificial intelligence in order to fix their tasks and priorities in this area, accelerate the pace of scientific, technical and socio-economic development. In the USA since 2019. There is a government "artificial intelligence initiative". The Americans approached its creation as an urgent issue of ensuring national security and preserving international leadership. This initiative includes eight strategies: long-term investments in AI research, development of effective methods of human-AI collaboration, understanding and consideration of ethical, legal and social AI, ensuring the safety and protection of AI systems, development of common publicly available datasets and environments for AI training and testing, evaluation of AI technology through standards and benchmarks indicators, a better understanding of the national workforce need in AI research and development, and the expansion of public-private partnerships to accelerate progress in AI [1]

China adopted the "Next Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan" back in 2017. In particular, the Plan provides for the introduction of AI technologies in industry, education, logistics, agriculture, etc., reducing the cost of AI-based equipment, the introduction of 5G technologies, the development of recognition technologies, decision-making, etc. Japan directs efforts in this area to increase industrial productivity, healthcare, medical care and welfare of citizens, mobility and information security. It is with the help of AI that Japan expects to bring to life the paradigms of the Fourth Industrial Revolution "Industry 4.0" and "Society 5.0" [1].

In France, AI technologies are developing primarily in the fields of health and the environment, transport and mobility, and security; in the UK – in biological sciences, public services, agriculture; in India, agriculture, healthcare, industry, energy, and education are among the priorities. In Norway, AI is the basis for the development of priority industries, which are healthcare, oil and gas, energy, the marine industry and the public sector [1]. Как следует из названных приоритетов развития ИИ в разных странах, правительства этих стран видят аналогичные возможности в области внедрения искусственного интеллекта. Они высоко оценивают потенциал ИИ для сохранения и, возможно, продвижения своих конкурентных позиций в стратегически значимых сферах деятельности. В планах разных стран чаще всего подчеркивается, что здравоохранение, технологии, сельское хозяйство и производство являются секторами с наибольшим потенциалом для прорывного развития с помощью ИИ. Правительства также осознают свою важную роль в создании платформ и

программ, поддерживающих обмен данными между государственным сектором и внешними заинтересованными сторонами для ускорения инноваций в области искусственного интеллекта. Общим элементом вышеупомянутых стратегий является необходимость соблюдения правил конфиденциальности и использования данных, касающихся проектирования, развертывания и использования систем искусственного интеллекта.

The introduction of digital technologies into the practice of public administration is also happening at a fairly rapid pace, although public administration systems have embarked on the path of using new digital technologies in their activities with some delay compared to the sphere of production. E-government projects began to take concrete shape when the leadership of a number of countries realized that "the transfer of new technologies based on innovative developments to the environment of public administration and public services can bring economic efficiency, since it reduces transaction costs and the cost of maintaining the bureaucratic apparatus, significantly optimizes budget expenditures in various areas of public administration" [2, p. 110].

E-government initiatives are aimed at optimizing government processes in order to make them more efficient, accessible and transparent to citizens. "The main features of e-government that distinguish it from the traditional bureaucratic model are a horizontally and vertically integrated system of interactions, consistency, openness, widespread electronic control, scale, efficiency, internal openness and mutual awareness, integration," notes Yu. V. Nikulina [3, p. 87]. However, the implementation and scaling of these digital infrastructures poses challenges related to their efficiency, big data management and the quality of services provided. Artificial intelligence has become a powerful tool for solving these problems, offering a wide range of possibilities – from process automation to predictive analytics. The growing interest in realizing the possibilities of the concept of e-government based on artificial intelligence is due to its potential to improve interaction between government agencies, citizens and businesses, thereby contributing to building trust, accessibility and accountability in the field of public services.

Artificial intelligence allows e-government platforms to offer users a personalized experience by adapting services based on a person's history, preferences and specific needs. Machine learning algorithms can analyze citizens' data to predict service needs, proactively review requests, and optimize application processes. For example, tax offices can be configured based on income data, previous tax returns, and financial behavior, allowing users to complete tax-related tasks faster and using more up-to-date information.

Artificial intelligence also allows you to automate routine administrative tasks such as processing applications, answering frequently asked questions and updating information. This reduces the burden on government employees, reduces operational costs and minimizes the risk of human error. Chatbots, for example, are increasingly being used in e-government services to process basic requests, freeing up resources for more complex tasks. In addition, robotic Process Automation (RPA) can manage document processing, data entry, and verification, making services faster and more efficient for both citizens and government agencies.

Predictive analytics based on artificial intelligence can provide useful information to governments, helping them make informed management decisions. By analyzing large amounts of data, artificial intelligence systems can predict trends such as population growth, infrastructure needs, or the spread of infectious diseases. This data-driven approach supports long-term planning, risk management and operational management. For example, AI can analyze

traffic data to improve urban planning or predict health resource needs based on demographic data.

Кибербезопасность является главной заботой современного государства, поскольку государственными органами обрабатывается большое число конфиденциальных данных о гражданах. ИИ предоставляет сложные инструменты для обнаружения угроз и реагирования на них, повышая безопасность системы. Алгоритмы машинного обучения могут выявлять необычные закономерности, указывающие на киберугрозы или мошенничество, в режиме реального времени, что позволяет быстрее реагировать на инциденты в сфере безопасности.

Governments can also use facial recognition and identity verification using AI to reduce the risk of identity fraud in government services. AI can play a central role in digital identity verification, which is a crucial aspect of e-government. AI-driven identity authentication systems provide secure real-time verification processes, facilitating online access to various government services. These systems can simplify and streamline processes such as voting, filing tax returns and documents, reducing bureaucracy and improving the quality of service to citizens.

Through the introduction of AI, e-government systems can increase transparency and accountability. AI can analyze and monitor government spending, identifying unusual transactions or potential cases of corruption. In addition, artificial intelligence-based data analysis platforms allow citizens to access real-time data on government activities, which increases public confidence and contributes to the creation of a more open management model.

Artificial intelligence provides continuous interaction and feedback collection, enabling governments to respond to public concerns and adapt policies accordingly. NLP algorithms can analyze public opinion on social networks or on e-government portals, providing governments with information about the needs and opinions of citizens. By using real-time feedback in decision-making processes, AI contributes to the creation of a participatory management model that dynamically adapts to public needs.

The predictive capabilities of AI can significantly help in policy planning, resource allocation, and crisis management. By analyzing trends and modeling results, AI systems can predict resource needs, anticipate the consequences of natural disasters, and propose preventive measures. For example, during the COVID 19 pandemic of the healthcare crisis, AI in China was used to track patterns of disease spread and effective allocation of medical resources [4, p. 53]. This ability to take proactive rather than reactive responses makes AI a vital tool for sustainable management.

The use of AI is possible not only at the state level, but also at the local level. Thus, "the synergy between AI and the Internet of Things (IoT) opens up new opportunities for electronic governance in smart cities. IoT devices in public places can generate real-time data, allowing AI systems to monitor and manage urban services such as traffic, waste collection, and public safety. Such integration can make urban governance more efficient and operational, which will benefit both public institutions and citizens" [2, p. 115].

It should also be noted that, in addition to the obvious benefits, the use of AI in e-government raises ethical issues related to data privacy and its use. Since governments handle sensitive personal information, AI systems must comply with the requirements of personal data protection legislation and maintain the trust of citizens. Concerns about the potential misuse of AI for surveillance and bias in decision-making algorithms require a strict regulatory framework to ensure ethical compliance.

In addition, the implementation of AI requires significant investments in infrastructure, including data storage, processing capabilities and system integration. Many government agencies lack the necessary technological infrastructure, which makes it difficult to implement AI. In addition, staff training in the management and operation of AI systems is essential for long-term success, but may require significant resources. Thus, the integration of AI involves high initial costs, especially for governments with limited budgets. Cost-effective strategies, such as phasing in AI and prioritizing high-impact areas, can mitigate financial constraints.

It should also be borne in mind that artificial intelligence systems largely depend on the quality and availability of data. The fragmentation of data, inaccuracies and lack of interaction between government agencies can reduce the effectiveness of AI in providing accurate analytical data and services. "Data management policy and interagency cooperation are necessary to ensure consistency, security and use of data in processes controlled by artificial intelligence," P. E. Strukova rightly notes [5, p. 591].

Effective implementation of AI in e-government systems also depends on citizen engagement and digital literacy. For widespread adoption, it is important that citizens are familiar with AI-enabled platforms and understand their functions. Therefore, Governments need to conduct public awareness campaigns and provide user-friendly interfaces to encourage use.

The future of AI for the implementation of the concept of e-government involves the development of completely new public services managed with the help of AI. For example, AI can form the basis of automated financial assistance programs, public health consulting services, or career guidance platforms, offering personalized recommendations and support based on user profiles and needs. These services increase the responsiveness of the government and simplify the interaction of citizens, which ultimately contributes to building public trust and satisfaction.

Artificial intelligence is able to modernize e-government by increasing the efficiency, personalization and transparency of public services. The possibilities of personalization based on artificial intelligence, predictive analytics and interaction with citizens in real time are enormous, which promises to improve the quality of public services and strengthen citizens' trust in digital governance. However, realizing the potential of AI in e-government systems requires solving problems related to ethics, infrastructure, data quality and citizen acceptance. With an appropriate regulatory framework, investments in digital infrastructure and a focus on transparency, AI can become the cornerstone of highly efficient e-government systems, stimulating innovation and contributing to the creation of a more responsive, inclusive and efficient public sector.

Summing up, it should be noted that the introduction of AI into such large-scale and complex systems of internal and external interactions as states should not only modernize, but also change their focus, quality and cost. The state digital infrastructure should be focused on solving important political, economic and social problems. It should provide citizens with access to open government information and provide objective data on the activities of government authorities in order to strengthen confidence in the State and its policies. An important task is also to organize interaction and constant dialogue between the state, citizens and civil society institutions, as well as to ensure the necessary level of public control over the activities of state bodies and organizations. The infrastructure should combine information resources and services of government agencies to strengthen the unified information space of the country and, ultimately, ensure the creation of a system of public network services that meets the real needs of the state and citizens.

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1. Governing AI for Humanity: Final Report [Electronic resource]. URL: https://www.un.org/sites/un2.un.org/files/governing_ai_for_humanity_final_report_en.pdf. (Date of access: 01.11.2024).
2. Ваславский, Я. Гобуев, С. Варианты развития электронного правительства опыт России, США, КНР // Международные процессы. 2017. Том 15, № 1. С. 108-125.
3. Никулина, Ю. В. Электронные коммуникации в системе государственного управления // Социальные коммуникации в современном мире : сборник научных статей по материалам работы Первого белорусского философского конгресса, Минск, 18–20 октября 2017 г. / БГУ, Фак. философии и социальных наук ; отв. ред.: Я. С. Яскевич, О. В. Терещенко, Ю. Ю. Гафарова. – Минск : БГУ, 2018. С. 86-89.
4. Филиппова, И. А. Правовое регулирование искусственного интеллекта: опыт Китая // Journal of Digital Technologies and Law. 2024. №2(1). С. 46-73.
5. Струкова П. Э. Искусственный интеллект в Китае: современное состояние отрасли и тенденции развития // Вестник Санкт-Петербургского университета. Востоковедение и африканистика. 2020 Т. 12. Вып. 4. С. 588-606.